

NASIGuide: Title Changes

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What is a title change?

For all serials, a title change is the addition, deletion, change, or reordering of any of the first five words in the title proper (the first six words if the title begins with an article). Also, the addition, deletion, or change of any word after the first five words counts as a change if it changes the title's meaning or the subject matter.

But, not all title changes will require a new serial record. Some changes can be recorded on the existing record by adding a note and/or a variant title for the title variation. Use the detailed rules in Anglo American Cataloguing Rules (2nd ed., 2002 rev.) (AACR2) chapter 21.2, the Library of Congress Rule Interpretations (LCRI's), and the CONSER Cataloging Manual (CONSER), module 16 to determine whether the change should result in a new record for the title.

What are major changes that require a new bibliographic record?

- A major change is when a word (or words) that affects access or the meaning or scope of the publication's subject matter is added, changed, rearranged, or dropped, according to CONSER Cataloging Manual 16.2.2.
- Also major is an addition, deletion, or a change of name in a corporate body that is responsible for publishing the title if it's the main entry, if used to qualify a uniform title (CONSER 16.1.1 and AACR2 3B), or at the beginning of the title.
- But a change in representation of the corporate name, (e.g. from an acronym to the full form of name, or vice versa) is considered only a minor change.
- And, if the title's physical format changes (e.g., from printed to electronic), a new record is required.

How do you to record a major change?

- First, close the now-ceased old title (CONSER 16.7). In the fixed MARC fields, change the publication status to indicate that it is ceased, and add the final year of publication to the dates. Use OCLC's Bibliographic Formats and Standards to find correct codes and format allowed in each field.
- In the variable MARC fields, add the final year of publication if known to any field which includes a range of dates. Consult CONSER 16.7 for detailed, field-by-field instructions. Record the final issue's numbering and date. The final step is to add a linking field (785) referring to the new title, including its ISSN and OCLC control number, if available.
- Once the old title is closed, create a record for the new title, following the CONSER Cataloging Manual Part 1 modules and AACR2 chapters 1, 12, 21, and 25 (plus their accompanying LCRI's) as needed.

- For integrating resources, replace the title proper in the original record with the new title and change the bibliographic description to cover the current title (AACR2 21.2C1), instead of creating a new record. When the main entry in an integrating resource changes, replace it on the original record with the latest corporate body name and add the older name in a note, if it's considered important (AACR2 21.3B1 and 12.1B8b).

What changes are considered minor, not requiring a new record?

- The change is minor when it involves variations in spelling, grammar, or punctuation, including spelling-out of words versus abbreviations or acronyms, or changes in articles, prepositions, or conjunctions in the title proper.
- A change in the order of a parallel title, the order of words in a list within the title, or in words linking the title to numbering are minor.
- A fluctuation from one title to another in a frequent, regular pattern is a minor change.
- And when words indicating the type of publication (such as “magazine”, “journal”, or “newsletter”) are added or dropped, it's also minor. For more discussion and additional examples of minor changes, see CONSER 16.2.3.
- Changes in numbering, even if the numbering reverts back to no. 1. In this case, the numbering should be updated in the 362 field (see CONSER 8.7). Other changes in numbering can be recorded in a note.

How do you record minor changes?

CONSER stipulates that when the change affects access within the first five words (or six if it begins with an article), it should be recorded in a note on the existing record, and also an added entry for the title variant (246 field) (CONSER module 7). But only a note is necessary if the change doesn't affect access (CONSER 16.2.3.).

For more information:

Websites

Cataloger's Reference Shelf. CONSER Cataloging Manual <http://www.itsmarc.com/crs/man1573.htm>

MARC 21 Concise Format for Bibliographic Data <http://www.loc.gov/marc/bibliographic/ecbdhome.html>

Books

Anglo-American Cataloging Rules, 2nd ed., 2002 rev., 2005 upd. Ottawa, Can. : Canadian Library Association ; London : Charter Institute of Library and Information Professionals ; Chicago, IL : American Library Association, 2002.

Bibliographic Formats and Standards, 4th ed. Dublin, OH: OCLC Online Computer Library Ctr., 2008.

CONSER cataloging manual, 2002 ed., Update 1, Spring 2004. [Washington, D.C.] : Library of Congress, Cataloging Distribution Service, 2002.

Library of Congress Rule Interpretations, rev. ed. Washington, D.C.: Cataloging Distribution Service, Library of Congress, 2000.

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